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Growth and phenotypic plasticity in *Aureobasidium pullulans* on lignin derivatives

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Phenotypic plasticity is the ability of any organism to respond to environmental signals by altering its morphology, physiological state, or behavior (West-Eberhard, 1989). *Aureobasidium pullulans* (de Bary) Arnaud (*A. pullulans*), a polymorphic black yeast-like fungus, exemplifies this capacity through its ability to modify its phenotype in response to environmental stimuli, enabling it to thrive under a wide range of climate conditions. This flexibility makes *A. pullulans* an exceptionally ideal candidate for the project "Bioinspired Living Skin for Architecture (ARCHI-SKIN)". By mimicking the natural process, the "ARCHI-SKIN" project is developing an innovative bioinspired living coating system based on fungal biofilm for protection of various building materials. To achieve the goal of this project, it is important to understand the mechanisms of fungal growth, including their ability to utilise diverse nutrients and form biofilms. This understanding is crucial for developing a technically applicable, controlled, and optimised biofilm that effectively protects substrate surfaces.

This present study aims to investigate the growth and phenotypic plasticity of *A. pullulans* on different lignin derivatives, namely vanillin, phenol, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid, and p-coumaric acid. The growth and morphologies of *A. pullulans* were visualised using a transmitted light imaging system (EVOS M7000, ThermoFisher Scientific), which captured projection images at defined time intervals. The acquired images were used for evaluating the morphological characteristics of the fungus. The obtained results revealed the variation in colony form, dimension, and morphologies of *A. pullulans* on different lignin derivatives, indicating the phenotypic plasticity of this fungus. This evaluation provides valuable insight into the dynamic interactions between *A. pullulans* and lignin breakdown products. Such insights are fundamental for optimising coating formulations, enhancing their effectiveness and durability in protecting building material surfaces, and contributing to sustainable and eco-friendly coating solutions.

Keywords: bioinspiration, living coatings, building materials, fungal growth, biofilm